

Towards living lab value proposition: Living lab experts' perceptions on living lab value

Authors

Teemu Santonen¹, Silia Petronikoulou², Despoina Petsani², Sarantis Dimitriadis², Panos Bamidis², Evdokimos Konstantinidis^{2,3}

¹ Laurea University of Applied Sciences, Vantaa, Finland

² Medical Physics and Digital Innovation Lab, Faculty of Health Sciences, School of Medicine, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Thessaloniki, Greece

³ European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL), Brussels, Belgium

Abstract

Prior studies have argued that the value what living labs are providing is blurry. Grounded on the Living Lab experts' opinions, the study aims to identify the key value proposition elements for Living Labs. An online workshop was arranged in which 22 experts provided a total of 209 value proposition suggestions. Participants were asked to generate value propositions for the following Living Lab customer groups and for different innovation process phases: researchers, policy makers and public authorities, and SMEs/companies. The suggestions were strongly relying on the activities that living labs are doing and resulted in an initial categorization of Living Lab values. In the follow-up process, expert arguments were used as a guidance for literature search, in which the following quantifiable value proposition elements were defined: 1) Economic benefits, 2) Improved innovation, 3) Better validity and reliability, 4) Benefits for the users and society, 5) Enhanced collaboration and networking possibilities, 6) Safe environment for RDI and 7) Increased skills and capabilities.

Key words

Value proposition, Expert opinion, Living lab benefits, Living lab value

Introduction

Living labs (LLs) are collaborative and user-centered environments that enable the co-creation and testing of new technologies, services, and systems in real-life contexts. According to the literature, a key-characteristic of Living Labs is that they promote and facilitate research and innovation through the collaboration and interaction between various stakeholders, such as universities and researchers, businesses, policy makers and citizens/users, by using a participatory approach (Leminen, Westerlund and Nyström, 2012; Schuurman, De Marez and Ballon, 2015; Sangiorgi, D., & Prendiville, 2018).

Customer value proposition (CVP) defines how an organization aims to provide value to customers (Payne, Frow and Eggert, 2017). From a customer-enterprise perspective, “value proposition” is a dynamic statement that explains and summarizes the benefits that a service, product or solution offers to its customers or users and why this product or service should be chosen over other similar, competitive options (Johnson, Christensen and Kagermann, 2008; Osterwalder and Pigneur, 2010). In the context of Living Labs, although the value proposition is not yet clearly defined, in this study it refers to the unique value or benefits that the Living Lab approach offers to its stakeholders. Living Lab stakeholders are either the Living Lab customers (a person or organization who purchases or uses living lab research infrastructure services to conduct a specific contract-based research) or end-users that are study participants who voluntarily participate in research after giving informed consent to be the subject of the research.

The aim of the present study is to identify the key elements of Living Lab value propositions from Living lab expert’s point of view, having as a starting point the Living Labs in the Health & Wellbeing domain.

What value living labs can provide for their customers

Who is a living lab customer?

Multi-stakeholder participation is one of the key elements of Living Labs, which are engaging all the actors of the Quadruple Helix innovation framework in their studies (Carayannis and Campbell, 2009). Grounded on Business Model Canvas (Osterwalder and Pigneur, 2010), a study by (Santonen et al., 2020) identified key customer segments of the quadruple helix for health and wellbeing Living Labs. Companies were represented by device manufacturers, digital service providers and preventive health/wellbeing service providers. Academia group included educational and research

organisations. Public sector organisations covered municipalities and cities, state level organisations, regional public authorities as well as primary, secondary, and tertiary care health organisation which depending on the country can also be private organisation. For civic society non-governmental organisation were referred. Networks and clusters were also mentioned, which can belong to multiple quadruple helix groups depending on their mission.

The aforementioned customer segments can be considered as Business-to-Business Customer (B2B) who purchase or use living lab research infrastructure services to conduct a specific contract based research and/or development activity. To clarify, in this study we are mainly interested to define value propositions for Living lab research infrastructure end users, not the study participants who are representing final end-users.

What value Living Labs provide

Existing literature and references discuss a plethora of benefits of the Living Lab approach, including increased user involvement and collaboration between multiple stakeholders and, consequently, better alignment with user needs and preferences (Følstad, A., & Kvale, 2018), more effective innovation processes and outcomes (Dell’Era and Landoni, 2014; Schuurman, De Marez and Ballon, 2015), faster time-to-market (European Commission, 2016), as well as improved product and service quality along with reduced risk of failure (Leminen, Westerlund and Nyström, 2012; Dell’Era and Landoni, 2014; Schuurman, De Marez and Ballon, 2015). Living Labs as open innovation ecosystems are noted for their ability to bridge the gap between research and development (Følstad, A., & Kvale, 2018) and, also, stimulate economic growth by providing a safe space for collaboration and experimentation (European Commission., 2016; Følstad, A., & Kvale, 2018). A study by (Santonen and Julin, 2019) evaluated what kind of needs and expectations SMEs have for using transnational living lab services. The main findings include 1) testing, 2) marketing/sales support, 2) R&D for new ideas, 3) networking and collaboration, 4) access to end-users, 5) market knowledge, 6) support for innovation management, localization/landing, and funding.

These benefits claims are not without critic. After extensive literature review (Paskaleva and Cooper, 2021) concluded that the actual Living Lab performance and benefits remains blurry. Authors also argue that the published evidence so far leans on inadequate research design and circular reasoning derived from the Living Lab definition is often utilized to arguing the benefits. As the value proposition of Living Labs is a crucial element that inspires stakeholders to collaborate with the Living Labs

and commit their time, resources, and knowledge, it is of utmost significance to explore this issue in more depth.

In order to robustly correspond to (Paskaleva and Cooper, 2021) claims regarding living lab performance and benefits, we must first understand what living lab experts themselves think about the value they can provide for their customers. Once the key elements of the value have been identified, then a robust empirical evaluation framework can be defined to validate these value arguments in further studies.

Methodology

Expert opinion evaluation and brainstorming as a research method

This study can be considered as an expert opinion evaluation, as the main target was to define the Living Lab value proposition from Living lab expert’s point of view. The utilization of expert knowledge is grounded on an assumption that using experts will lead to better results than using from non-‘experts’ (Goodman, 1987). However, prior studies have challenged this assumption, but the research approach is commonly used in scientific studies and therefore suitable for our research purposes (Sackman, 1975; Baker, Lovell and Harris, 2006). Open-ended questions were used for collecting value proposition suggestions. The advantage of open-ended questions is that they encourage respondents to expand on their thoughts, providing more intricate and nuanced responses, stimulate creativity and innovation, leading to new insights and ideas and facilitating the generation of new hypotheses for further investigation (Kvale, 1996; Rubin and Rubin, 2011).

Formation of an expert panel

Horizon 2020 funded Virtual health and wellbeing Living Lab Infrastructure (VITALISE) project’s Harmonization Body members were representing Living Lab experts. VITALISE project aims to open up Living Lab research infrastructures as a means to facilitate and promote research activities in the Health and Wellbeing domain in Europe and beyond, as well as harmonise processes and common tools commonly utilized by living labs. The VITALISE Harmonization Body consists of VITALISE partner representatives, people that are currently working in Living Labs of the ENoLL network as well as professionals with expertise in Health and Wellbeing and ICT domain.

Data collection process description and response

The data collection took place during the VITALISE Harmonization Body meeting was

held virtually, on the 17th of January 2023. The participants were asked to report through the mentimeter platform their opinions regarding the value they consider that the Living Labs can actually offer. In particular, 22 participants joined the Harmonization Body meeting and provide anonymously their suggestions about the value that Living Labs provide to each of the following customer groups 1) researchers, 2) policy makers and public authorities, and 3) SMEs/companies. They were also asked to define the Living Lab value proposition for different Technology Readiness Level phases (TRL 1-9). The Technology Readiness Level (TRL) scales are commonly used and widely accepted framework for assessing the maturity of technologies and describing the current innovation process stage (Héder, 2017). The TRL value proposition was grouped in three levels, as the researchers have identified that there no major changes among these levels that can be clearly depicted in the value proposition (TRL 1-3, TRL 4-6, TRL 7-9).

On average the available time for them to answer was ca. five minutes for each question. After each question, the results were shown to respondents and they had a possibility to comment on the outcomes. Everyone was able to submit multiple answers for each question. In total, 57 answers were collected regarding the value propositions for the researchers, 32 for the policy makers and public authorities and 46 for the SMEs/companies. Regarding value proposition related to TRLs, 26 answers were collected for TRL 1-3, 27 answers for TRL 4-6 and 21 answers for TRL7-9. In all 209 value proposition suggestions were provided.

Data analysis process

All the 209 answers were analysed as a combined dataset in order to define the Living Lab value proposition. The differentiation in customer groups and TRL level was not taken into account in the analysis and the initial use of different questions was aiming at stimulating the participants new ideas generation. The data analysis was performed in three steps: 1) initial coding and categorization by 2 independent researchers, 2) consensus workshop among an experienced researchers' group, 3) formulation of the value proposition definitions by the research team.

The coding process proposed by (Saldaña, 2021) was applied from 2 independent researchers using a combination of deductive codes drawn from the prior research (Santonen and Julin, 2019; Santonen et al., 2020) and inductive codes generated by the Living Labs expert's arguments. After the initial coding, a categorization and grouping of answers was performed based on the assigned codes.

After the initial categorization, a consensus workshop took place among the core research group in order to align the results, identify similarities and differences and result to a common categorization strategy. The final step, included a deeper analysis of the resulted categories, including the definition of each category and the correlation of the results with elements coming from scientific literature regarding the value of Living Labs. The literature search was used to complement the results rather than compare and make changes.

Results

The analysis identified seven categories, and a mapping to existing literature was performed for each category. Table 1 presents the mapping, along with living lab expert arguments based on the final classification results, and the corresponding benefits derived from scientific literature covering various collaborative innovation terms (Santonen, 2021). In the discussion section, each value category is discussed in-depth, and corresponding scientific literature is referenced. The value proposition elements were classified into the following seven main categories based on the coding process: 1) economic benefits, 2) improved innovation, 3) better validity, 4) benefits for users and society, 5) enhanced collaboration, 6) safe development environment, and 7) capacity building.

Table 1. Living lab expert value argument mapping and generalised benefits from existing literature

Living lab expert arguments	Benefits derived from literature relating arguments
Economic benefits	
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Living lab can provide funding (e.g., via open calls) 2. Support to gain investments 3. Faster development time 4. Fail fast 5. Risk reduction 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Cost savings, 2. Reduced development costs, 3. Increased Efficiency, 4. Shorter time-to-market, 5. Funding
Improved innovation	
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Better solutions 2. Prioritization 3. State of the art / current status 4. Local and Internationalization market knowledge / marketing 5. Marketing support 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Better product design, 2. Improved quality, 3. Better problem solving, 4. Better decision making, 5. Competitive advantage, 6. Increased creativity and innovation, 7. Access to new markets
Validity and reliability	
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Living labs have extensive methodological expertise 2. Real-life 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Enhanced ecological validity, 2. Improved external validity, 3. Better generalizability,

3. Test, Validation / impact analysis (Iterative validation)	4. Increased validity,
4. Proof of concept	5. Richer data,
5. Risk reduction	6. Complementary insights
Benefits for the users and society	
1. Verified user acceptance	1. Enhanced User Experience
2. Needs and wants	2. Improved User / customer Satisfaction
3. Identification and definition of relevant target groups for your study purposes	3. Enhanced Social and Environmental Impact
4. Needs and requirements	
Enhanced collaboration and networking possibilities	
1. Providing access to user and engaging them across different innovation process phases	1. Increased Opportunities for Collaboration
2. Networking and collaboration opportunities	2. Improved Communication and Collaboration:
3. Multi/Interdisciplinary	3. Enhanced Collaboration
4. Innovation network orchestration	4. Strengthened Partnerships and Networks
5. Panel management	5. Increased Stakeholder Engagement and Ownership
6. Co-creation	6. Greater Access to Participants
7. Engagement / Involvement / feedback	7. Increased Efficiency
8. Publications	8. Improved Resource Allocation
Safe environment for RDI	
Ethics	Protecting Human Participants
Risk reduction	Upholding Public Trust
	Ensuring Fairness
	Promoting Integrity
	Preventing Research Misconduct
	Meeting Legal Requirements
	Regulatory Compliance
Increased skills and capabilities	
Capacity building	
1. Skills to do user centric innovations	
2. Understanding agile/iterative/ innovation process	

Discussion

The resulting categories and sub-elements for each category have also been identified in the literature to some extent. An attempt was made to provide a more in-depth explanation and presentation of the categories, taking into account the existing findings on the value that Living Labs offer.

Economic benefits refer to gains that can be expressed in financial terms resulting from the Living Lab innovation process or the improvement of the developed solution (modified from Oxford Reference, 2023). A common approach in European Commission funded projects is competitive open call funding. Many project examples, such as the Health Innovation Center of Southern Denmark (2017), show that Living Labs offer

money to companies and researchers to conduct Living Lab research. Additionally, startup companies often struggle to find their first customers, which are needed to convince investors. Therefore, a Living Lab study verifying customer acceptance and other solution benefits can help assure investors.

Fail fast refers to an iterative innovation process that involves quick testing to identify and address potential problems as early as possible (Müller and Thoring, 2012) and is a common approach used in design thinking and lean startup methodologies. Additionally, the risk of solution failure is greatly reduced since many problems can be detected at the beginning of the development process, where making changes is cheaper (von Hippel, 1993). Early problem detection can also reduce time to market, enabling faster revenues.

Improved innovation refers to all the different aspects in which the developed solution, whether it be a product, service, process, decision, policy, etc., could be better than competing solutions. The key idea of the Living Lab process is to improve the design and user experience quality of the developed solution (De Moor et al., 2010). Better user experience typically includes factors such as usability, accessibility, functionality, desirability, credibility, and efficiency (Hassenzahl and Tractinsky, 2006; Sauer et al., 2020; Barnum and Palmer, 2010). Living Lab studies have referred to better design in terms of functionality, usability, sustainability, and cost-effectiveness (Brankaert and Den Ouden, 2017; Liedtke et al., 2012; Fleet, 2020). Living Labs are also argued to widen the scope of innovation, stimulate creativity, and facilitate better decision-making and policymaking, especially when dealing with complex societal challenges and problems (Barata et al., 2017; Sörvik et al., 2015; Liedtke et al., 2012; Gatta et al., 2017). As a result, improved innovation should eventually lead to a competitive advantage if proper competitor analysis and high user acceptance have been achieved during the Living Lab process.

Validity and reliability are also factors of Living Lab value proposition, with reliability referring to the stability of findings and validity to the truthfulness of findings (Altheide & Johnson, 1994). Living Lab research, driven by design thinking, combines laboratory-based and field-based approaches to ensure better validity and reliability. The use of real-life settings with real users in Living Lab studies results in high ecological validity, meaning that findings can be generalized or applied to real-world situations (Cronbach, 1957). The combination of laboratory- and field-based approaches also increases validity, as they complement each other's strengths and weaknesses. Living Lab research designs follow a multistakeholder approach, leading to larger and more diverse sample populations covering all quadruple helix actors, resulting in more

grounded study results. The multimethod requirement derived from the Living Lab definition strengthens external validity, extending research findings beyond the sample population and research context.

Benefits for users and society refers to the impact of Living Lab studies in these groups. User-centricity is at the heart of the Living Lab approach, where research and innovation activities prioritize the needs, behaviors, and preferences of users (Eriksson et al. 2005). By involving users as active participants in the Living Lab process, the developed solutions are more likely to meet their needs, leading to higher user adoption and retention rates. In addition, the Public-Private-People Partnership (4P) approach of Living Labs provides a way to legitimize the results across society, ensuring that the solutions developed are not only effective but also socially acceptable and sustainable (Molinari, 2011).

Enhanced collaboration and networking possibilities is another value that Living Labs offer. Collaboration lies at the core of participatory design and co-creation. Living Labs offer a wide range of tools and methodologies to enhance collaboration among the quadruple helix stakeholders (Kalinauskaite et al. 2021). These tools mainly focus on communication among the stakeholders, increasing transparency and trust, which is essential for successful collaboration. Effective communication strategies used by Living Labs increase stakeholder engagement, facilitating the creation and management of a long-term panel of engaged stakeholders. This expands the value that Living Labs can offer as they have access to a greater number of potential participants. Another advantage of Living Labs is that they enable more diverse and multidisciplinary collaborations, bringing together stakeholders from different industries and fields (Hakkarainen and Hyysalo, 2013). This fosters cross-sectoral and interdisciplinary collaboration, opening up new and sometimes unexplored opportunities for cooperation.

Safe environment for RDI refers to the provision of the mechanisms for ensuring regulatory and legal compliance. Living Labs provide mechanisms to ensure stakeholders' rights are protected and ethical considerations are integrated into technological research (Callari et al. 2020). However, this adoption of an ethical approach is not just a one-off consideration for specific projects, but rather fostered over the long-term with stakeholders, building trust and establishing environments for democratic and fair dialogues. These real-life environments are considered safe for experimentation due to the trust of ecosystem actors and systematic approaches of Living Labs that pay special attention to how to experiment in real-life settings. In today's context, with the emergence and application of regulations such as GDPR, most

Living Labs have ethics experts who are involved in the protocol design of the experiment. Additionally, there is a trend towards equally acknowledging the stakeholders involved in scientific publications and setting their own participation rules for Living Lab experiments.

Increased skills and capabilities. The term 'capacity building' can have various interpretations (Simmons et al., 2011). For the purpose of this study, capacity building is defined as a process that enhances the knowledge, skills, and abilities of individuals, organizations, or communities to understand the key principles of the Living Lab approach. By acquiring new knowledge and skills, these actors can initiate or undertake their own Living Lab projects or become proficient end-users of Living Lab research infrastructure. Living Labs can transfer the knowledge and experience that they have acquired in a comprehensive and effective way.

Conclusions

Living labs have been criticized for the lack of clarity around the value they provide. To address this, we conducted a study to identify the key elements of the Living Lab value proposition, drawing on the perspectives of Living Lab experts. During an online workshop, experts express their opinions on the value Living Labs are offering for the research and development community and the importance of Living Lab activities. These arguments were used as a guide for a literature search, which led us to identify seven benefits of Living Labs: economic benefits, improved innovation, better validity and reliability, benefits for users and society, enhanced collaboration and networking possibilities, a safe environment for RDI, and increased skills and capabilities.

While our study was based on expert perceptions and scientific literature, future studies should aim to define quantifiable measures for evaluating the suggested value propositions. This study can also contribute to the work that is being performed by Koen et. al (2022) that aims to define the evaluation framework of Living Labs. Our results can serve as a roadmap and checklist for Living Labs as they consider the value they can provide to their customers. Further research to produce quantifiable results on each of these domains should be also done in order to strengthen the Living Lab position in the research and innovation ecosystem.

Funding details

This research was funded by VITALISE - Virtual health and wellbeing Living Lab Infrastructure– funded by the Horizon 2020 Framework Programme of the European Union for Research Innovation. Grant agreement number: 101007990.

References

1. Altheide, D.L. and Johnson, J.M. (1994) 'Criteria for assessing interpretive validity in qualitative research.'
2. Baker, J., Lovell, K. and Harris, N. (2006) 'How expert are the experts? An exploration of the concept of 'expert' within Delphi panel techniques', *Nurse researcher*, 14(1).
3. Barata, F.T. et al. (2017) 'Creative innovation and related living lab experiences: A mediterranean model', Évora: Cátedra UNESCO [Preprint].
4. Barnum, C.M. and Palmer, L.A. (2010) 'More than a feeling: understanding the desirability factor in user experience', in CHI'10 Extended Abstracts on Human Factors in Computing Systems, pp. 4703-4716.
5. Brankaert, R.G.A. and Den Ouden, P.H. (2017) 'The design-driven living lab: a new approach to exploring solutions to complex societal challenges', *Technology Innovation Management Review*, 7(1), pp. 44-51.
6. Callari TC, Moody L, Saunders J, Ward G, Woodley J. Stakeholder Requirements for an Ethical Framework to Sustain Multiple Research Projects in an Emerging Living Lab Involving Older Adults. *Journal of Empirical Research on Human Research Ethics*. 2020;15(3):111-127. doi:10.1177/1556264619873790
7. Carayannis, E.G. and Campbell, D.F.J. (2009) "'Mode 3'and'Quadruple Helix": toward a 21st century fractal innovation ecosystem', *International journal of technology management*, 46(3-4), pp. 201-234.
8. Cronbach, L.J. (1957) 'The two disciplines of scientific psychology.', *American psychologist*, 12(11), p. 671.
9. De Moor, K. et al. (2010) 'Proposed framework for evaluating quality of experience in a mobile, testbed-oriented living lab setting', *Mobile Networks and applications*, 15, pp. 378-391.
10. Dell'Era, C. and Landoni, P. (2014) 'Living Lab: A methodology between user-centred design and participatory design', *Creativity and Innovation Management*, 23(2), pp. 137-154.
11. Eriksson, M., Niitamo, V.-P. and Kulkki, S. (2005) 'State-of-the-art in utilizing Living Labs approach to user-centric ICT innovation-a European approach', Lulea: Center for Distance-spanning Technology. Lulea University of Technology Sweden: Lulea [Preprint].
12. European Commission. (2016) 'Living labs: A multi-stakeholder approach to innovation.', Publications Office of the European Union [Preprint].
13. Fleet, R. (2020) 'A Canadian Rural Living Lab Hospital: Implementing solutions for improving rural emergency care', *Future healthcare journal*, 7(1), p. 15.
14. Følstad, A., & Kvale, K. (2018) 'Living Labs as Open Innovation Systems for Research & Development: A Review of Literature. *Innovation: Management, Policy & Practice*', pp. 20(2), 155-185.
15. Gatta, V., Marcucci, E. and Le Pira, M. (2017) 'Smart urban freight planning process: integrating desk, living lab and modelling approaches in decision-making', *European Transport Research Review*, 9(3), p. 32. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12544-017-0245-9>.
16. Goodman, C.M. (1987) 'The Delphi technique: a critique', *Journal of advanced nursing*, 12(6), pp. 729-734.
17. Hakkarainen, L., & Hyysalo, S. 2013. How Do We Keep the Living Laboratory Alive? Learning and Conflicts in Living Lab Collaboration. *Technology Innovation Management Review*, 3(12): 16-22. <http://doi.org/10.22215/timreview/749>
18. Hassenzahl, M. and Tractinsky, N. (2006) 'User experience-a research agenda', *Behaviour & information technology*, 25(2), pp. 91-97.
19. Health Innovation Center of Southern Denmark (2017) Product Validation in Health -Evaluating transnational testing in Baltic Sea Region Living Labs. Available at: <https://scanbalt.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/03/ProVaHealth-Evaluating-transnational-testing-in-Baltic-Sea-Region-Living-Labs.pdf> (Accessed: 4 May 2023).
20. Héder, M. (2017) 'From NASA to EU: the evolution of the TRL scale in Public Sector Innovation', *The Innovation Journal*, 22(2), pp. 1-23.

21. Johnson, M.W., Christensen, C.M. and Kagermann, H. (2008) 'Reinventing your business model', *Harvard business review*, 86(12), pp. 50–59.
22. Kalinauskaite I, Brankaert R, Lu Y, Bekker T, Brombacher A and Vos S 2021 Facing Societal Challenges in Living Labs: Towards a Conceptual Framework to Facilitate Transdisciplinary Collaborations Sustainability 13 614 Online: <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/su13020614>.
23. Kvale, S. (1996) 'Interviews: An introduction to qualitative research interviewing', Sage publications [Preprint].
24. Leminen, S., Westerlund, M. and Nyström, A.-G. (2012) 'Living labs as open-innovation networks'.
25. Liedtke, C. et al. (2012) 'LIVING LAB: user-driven innovation for sustainability', *International journal of sustainability in higher education*, 13(2), pp. 106–118.
26. Molinari, F. (2011) 'Living labs as multi-stakeholder platforms for the egovernance of innovation', in *Proceedings of the 5th international conference on theory and practice of electronic governance*, pp. 131–140.
27. Müller, R.M. and Thoring, K. (2012) 'Design thinking vs. lean startup: A comparison of two user-driven innovation strategies', *Leading through design*, 151(2).
28. Osterwalder, A. and Pigneur, Y. (2010) *Business model generation: a handbook for visionaries, game changers, and challengers*. John Wiley & Sons.
29. Oxford Reference (2023) Economic benefit. Available at: <https://www.oxfordreference.com/display/10.1093/oi/authority.20110803095741313> (Accessed: 26 April 2023).
30. Paskaleva, K. and Cooper, I. (2021) 'Are living labs effective? Exploring the evidence', *Technovation*, 106, p. 102311.
31. Payne, A., Frow, P. and Eggert, A. (2017) 'The customer value proposition: evolution, development, and application in marketing', *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 45, pp. 467–489.
32. Rubin, H.J. and Rubin, I.S. (2011) *Qualitative interviewing: The art of hearing data*. sage.
33. Sackman, H. (1975) 'Delphi Critique, Expert Opinion, Forecasting and Group Processes/H', Sackman-Lexington, Mass.: Lexington Books [Preprint].
34. Saldaña, J. (2021) 'The coding manual for qualitative researchers', *The coding manual for qualitative researchers*, pp. 1–440.
35. Sangiorgi, D., & Prendiville, A. (2018) 'Exploring the future of living labs: A literature review.', *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 170, pp. 18–29.
36. Santonen, T. (2021) 'Clarifying terminology for collaborative innovation and development', *Innovating our common future, Proceedings ISPIM Berlin 2021* [Preprint].
37. Santonen, T. and Julin, M. (2019) 'How transnational living labs can help SMEs to internationalise', *International Journal of Innovation Management*, 23(08), p. 1940003.
38. Santonen, T. et al. (2020) 'Living lab business models and services – Key findings from Product Validation in Health (Pro-VaHealth) project', p. 66.
39. Sauer, J., Sonderegger, A. and Schmutz, S. (2020) 'Usability, user experience and accessibility: towards an integrative model', *Ergonomics*, 63(10), pp. 1207–1220.
40. Schuurman, D., De Marez, L. and Ballon, P. (2015) 'Living Labs: a systematic literature review', *Open Living Lab Days 2015* [Preprint].
41. Simmons, A., Reynolds, R.C. and Swinburn, B. (2011) 'Defining community capacity building: is it possible?', *Preventive medicine*, 52(3–4), pp. 193–199.
42. Sörvik, J., Rollof, J. and West, S. (2015) *Creativity Labs in the Öresund Region*. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.1899.6563>.
43. Vervoort, K., Trousse, B., Desole, M., Bamidis, P., Konstantinidis, E., Santonen, T., Petsani, D., Servais, D., De Boer, D., Spagnoli, F. and Onur, O., 2022. Harmonizing the evaluation of living labs: A standardized evaluation framework. In *Proceedings of the XXXIII ISPIM Innovation Conference*. Lappeenranta teknillinen yliopisto.
44. von Hippel, E. (1993) 'Wettbewerbsfaktor Zeit', *Moderne Industrie* [Preprint].

